

HYPERTROPHY AND MORBIDITY IN PATHOLOGY

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Abstract:

Nowadays, various types of diseases are common among the population. There are many factors that lead to such a pathological process. For this reason, the number of overweight and healthy people increases, and various diseases such as cardiovascular diseases and injuries of the endocrine system occur in them. The purpose of this research is to produce more software and production than the people who are burdened by the burden.

Keywords: *obesity, hypersthenic, hypodynamia, overweight, diabetes, hypertension, inactivity.*

Introduction

Material research methods. For the purpose of research, the anthropometric measurements of 425 residents of Yangiravot MFY, Okdarya District, Samarkand Region, were checked. Their height, weight, head circumference, chest circumference measurements were taken and analyzed. Anthropometric measurements determine the normal constitution of the body, determine which group it belongs to, and suggest which diseases are more likely to occur in this group (compared to nomosthenic, hyposthenic, hypersthenic). In addition, the body mass index (BMI) was required to be calculated. Through calculations, people in the category of overweight compared to the norm were known and it is defined as follows: TVI of each person was determined by dividing the square of the weight (in kilograms) by the height (in meters), and overweight with a body mass index above 30 and 84 patients were identified from a total of 425 residents in the obesity category. We focused on overweight and obese patients with a body mass index greater than 30 and found out which diseases they are more prone to. Adipose tissue can be filled in excess amount in physiological reserves, and accumulate in the mammary glands, thighs, abdomen. Currently, obesity is a chronic metabolic disease observed at any age. It is manifested as an increase in body weight

mainly due to fat tissue. The general morbidity and mortality of the population is increasing. In a developed society, even if there is no change in genetics, that is, regardless of genetic factors, obesity is increasing sharply. According to some data, about 20% of the world's population will suffer from obesity in 2025. If this continues, overweight and obesity will certainly pose a great threat to human health. Hypodynamia, disorder of rational nutrition, and the factors related to it are the reason for the increase of obesity among the population. As a result, diabetes, hypertension, kidney and liver diseases appear as a complication of obesity. Based on the results of the following examination, it was determined which diseases individuals in the overweight category are prone to. As a result of disturbances in the metabolism of fats in the body, their absorption, cell anabolism and catabolism change, as a result of which they begin to accumulate. And this disables the metabolism of cholesterol, triglycerides, and high molecular fatty acids.

Results and their analysis. The results of the analysis showed that 58 (69%) of the 84 overweight and obese patients were women. The remaining 26 (31%) were men. 60 (71.4%) of the overweight and obese individuals among the examined population were found to be only overweight in the 1st degree of obesity, and their TVI was noted to be in the range of 30-34.9. The remaining 24 persons (28.6%) were found to have only 2 degrees of obesity, and TVI was 35-39.9. We analyzed the percentage of disease occurrence of these individuals taking into account their overall overweight. 10 of these patients (12%) have persistent arterial hypertension, and 5 (6%) have diabetes. In addition, in rare cases of obese people, 2 (2.4%) had kidney failure, and 1 (1.2%) had polyarthritis. In the analysis of the results, people in this category have diabetes along with hypertension, and they make up 4 (4.76%) people. People with diabetes always have arterial hypertension. Violation of carbohydrate metabolism is certainly caused by various pathological processes in the cardiovascular system. Among the remaining patients, partial liver cirrhosis was detected in 1 (1.2%), fatty dystrophy of the heart in 2 (2.38%) and atherosclerosis in 2 (2.38%) residents.

Conclusion: The conclusion of the research is that it is necessary to eliminate a number of negative factors such as inactivity, non-compliance with the diet, stress, smoking and alcohol consumption, which cause the occurrence of disease among the population. Taking into account the individual background of each person, it is possible to prevent the possibility of disease by eliminating the following in the case of overweight: 1 - hypodynamia (inactivity) as a result of blood circulation disorders, pathologies of the musculoskeletal system. 2- Rational eating disorder (eating more fat). 3- smoking, alcoholism (damage to lungs, heart and blood vessels, liver) are more common.

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